

DEVELOPING THE SPEECH ACTIVITY OF THE FUTURE TEACHERS BASED ON PEDAGOGICAL DESIGN AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

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Abstract. *This article presents the personal views of pedagogues, psychologists, and methodologists on the current laws and stages of developing speech activity based on pedagogical design, creativity, self-management, and self-development competence in educational subjects, as well as the formation of knowledge, skills, and competencies on designing in educational activities, and expresses a subjective attitude to them.*

Keywords: *pedagogical design, knowledge, skills, competencies, self-management, self-development competence, laws, criteria, stages, cognitive education, pedagogical process, creative-pragmatic approach, educational activities, information technologies.*

Introduction

Today, one of the main professional tasks in the educational and pedagogical process is to develop students' speech, communicative, cognitive, pragmatic, and creative activities using modern methods and advanced information technologies and to guide them in applying these skills in practice. Achieving quality and efficiency in the educational process and raising it to a high level is directly related to the teacher's ability to carry out pedagogical design and develop students' speech activity. Furthermore, in developing the speech activity of future teachers through pedagogical design, it is essential to properly organize activities that help improve competencies such as speaking, listening, understanding, reading comprehension, and information processing, based on their creativity. Various views and approaches have been expressed regarding the development of pedagogical design skills in future teachers.

The experimental work we conducted on pedagogical design involved future teachers—students of higher education institutions—as the main participants. The focus was on their acquired knowledge regarding speech-cognitive and professional-communicative activities. In his dissertation "Theoretical Foundations of Organizing Creative Primary Education" Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences B.R. Adizov emphasizes that future primary school teachers can only achieve positive outcomes through their knowledge and experience of activity methods, way of thinking, and emotional-value-based attitude [1] towards reality. The pedagogical design activity of future teachers is founded on their knowledge, experience, and value-based thinking, alongside their ability to think creatively and intellectually.

Creative-communicative thinking plays a significant role in the development of pedagogical design competence. The more creatively a future teacher approaches a task and can correctly apply their knowledge in practice, the more their pedagogical design skills improve. It is essential to ensure creative independence based on responsibility, considering the goals and objectives of pedagogical design. Possessing both theoretical and practical knowledge, as well as developing aesthetically, ethically, axiologically, and communicatively, contributes significantly

to self-development. In this aspect, it is important to teach students to use modern advanced technologies in the educational process.

In this regard, Sh.T. Boltaeva states: "Their active participation in the educational process contributes to their moral, creative, and social development. In the design process, the aim is to solve specific pedagogical and technological tasks, create and construct an idea, and deliver useful outcomes in practice [2]."

Professor N.A. Muslimov outlines three stages in the design of the educational process:

- defining learning objectives and outcomes;
- developing assessment tasks and criteria based on the outcomes;
- creating a technological map (lesson plan map) of the learning process.

In the textbook *"Professional Pedagogy"* [3] by scholars B.X. Khodjayev, J.U.Shonazarov, and Z.T. Rakhimov, it is noted that in designing the learning process, it is appropriate to clearly define the content, goals, and expected outcomes of education; select appropriate methods, forms, and tools; develop clear criteria for assessing students' knowledge, skills, and competencies; and effectively organize them within the allotted time, ensuring they are harmonized.

In her article *"Pedagogical Process Design as an Educational Innovation"*, D. Khidirova lists the following principles of educational process design:

1. The effectiveness of educational design depends on clearly outlining all components (technological processes, management, tools, information, and socio-economic support);
2. Technological tools should be selected according to students' individual characteristics;
3. Design strategies should align with the teacher's individual style;
4. The quality of design depends on feedback (between teacher and student), the content of the design, and the effectiveness of all contributing factors [4].

Importantly, there are two levels in the structure of design activity: the creative level, aimed at generating new knowledge through design, and the individual level, reflecting the teacher's personality through designs based on studying experienced educators' practices.

Developing future teachers' speech activity through pedagogical design involves integrating theoretical-pedagogical and practical-methodological training to achieve professional quality and effectiveness. G.E. Muravyova includes in design skills: diagnosing the outcomes of didactic process development, planning implementation, constructing the technological process for creating material resources, and modeling new information about the object. [5]

V.A. Slastenin and N.V. Kuzmina define a set of competencies determining theoretical preparedness for design activities, including:

- reflective competence, ensuring self-improvement in pedagogical activities;
- cognitive competence, developing the ability to improve methodological knowledge;
- informational competence, acquiring and applying knowledge and skills; communicative competence, developing oral and written communication skills;
- social competence, aimed at understanding the essence of professional competency. This set of competencies and skills helps realize both the creative and individual levels of activity, ultimately leading to mastering pedagogical design competence. [6]

"The credit-module system is a process of organizing education, which is a set of modular technologies of education and an assessment model based on credit measurement. Its

implementation as a whole is a multifaceted and complex systematic process. The credit-module principle emphasizes two main issues: ensuring independent work of students; assessing students' knowledge based on ratings.

The following are recognized as the main tasks of the credit-module system:

- organizing educational processes on a modular basis; determining the value of one subject, course (credit);
- assessing students' knowledge based on rating points;
- enabling students to individually design their own curriculum; increasing the share of independent learning in the educational process;
- ensuring the convenience of educational programs and the possibility of changing them based on the demand for specialists in the labor market [7].”

“The main means of independent learning are independent educational materials. They are an integral system, different from textbooks, teaching aids and lecture texts. They contain deep and meaningful methodological instructions, a block for managing the cognitive activity of the learner, criteria for independent learning in the process of professional training, psychological and pedagogical recommendations for his self-direction towards independent learning, self-control, self-expression and self-assessment in the process of personal cognitive activity. Independent educational materials are in the form of teaching aids, lecture texts, computer programs, audio and video materials, recommendations on the use of existing traditional textbooks, and other sources of information [8].” The strategic content of independent learning in the development of the speech activity of future teachers based on pedagogical design is related to the following:

In the process of education, along with developing the learning abilities of future teachers, it is also important to focus on fostering their creativity, diagnostic skills, and the ability to design strategic plans for their future professional activities. [9] Enhancing future teachers' speech activity, as well as developing their critical thinking, creativity, and communication skills, opens the way to solving various pedagogical challenges.

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